

Traumatic Dental Injury for Primary Teeth

Abdulaziz Abdullah Alsaif*

King Saud University / Prince Abdulrahman Advanced Dental Institute, Saudi Arabia

Citation: Abdulaziz Abdullah Alsaif, Traumatic Dental Injury for Primary Teeth. *Int Case Rep Jour.* 2022;2(1):1-2.

Received Date: 20 January, 2022; **Accepted Date:** 24 January, 2022; **Published Date:** 26 January, 2022

***Corresponding author:** Abdulaziz Abdullah Alsaif, King Saud University / Prince Abdulrahman Advanced Dental Institute, Saudi Arabia

Copyright: © Abdulaziz Abdullah Alsaif, Open Access 2022. This article, published in *Int Case Rep Jour (ICRJ)* (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

CLINICAL IMAGE

3 years old Saudi male patient was booked for my clinic after initial pedodontics screening in October 2018. Chief complaint, according to father “My son has displaced tooth in his upper gum”

For medical history, the patient is healthy (ASA I) not under any medication, no reported allergy and vaccination up to date. History of dental trauma the child fallen with a feeding bottle one and half years ago in the Living room. According to Frankl classification he is Frankl II Negative. Intra oral and radiographic examination shows primary dentition stage, apically intruded tooth #51 (Figure1).

Figure 1: A and B are the clinical photos, C is the lateral radiograph, and D is the periapical radiograph.

The treatment plan for this case was extraction of tooth #51. The treatment done under nitrous oxide inhalation sedation, and we use local anesthesia Lidocaine 2% w/Epi 1:100,000. **Figure 2** shows the tooth after extraction.

Figure2: Tooth #51 after extraction.

The child had a 6-month recall appointment and the clinical and radiographic examination showed everything was within normal limit and tooth #11 had a normal eruption (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3: A and B are the clinical photos in the 6-month recall appointment, C is the periapical radiograph in the 6-month recall appointment